
PATGOV

The Governance of the European Patent System

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement MSCA-799203

POLICY BRIEF

June 2020

Please cite as:

N.S. Groenendijk (2020), *The Governance of the European Patent System – Policy brief*, Oslo: Oslo Metropolitan University.

This policy brief gives an overview of the background to and main results of the PATGOV project, a Marie Skłodowska Curie Action fellowship project, that ran from June 2018 until May 2020, at Oslo Metropolitan University. It first describes the background of the project by summarizing the current main criticisms of the European patent system. It then briefly explains the research undertaken. The final part consists of policy recommendations.

The full Final research report (which includes all the academic references and project output) can be found at: <https://www.oslomet.no/en/research/research-projects/patgov>.

BACKGROUND TO THE PATGOV PROJECT

The multi-level and fragmented European patent system has been criticized for a number of reasons. Some have addressed *performance deficiencies* of the system, emphasizing the decreasing quality of patents (including back-logs in patent assessment) and/or the –high- level of the patent fees in Europe, often from the perspective of increased global competition between the so-called IP5 offices (USPTO, EPO, JPO, KIPO, and SIPO).

From a (*bio-ethical*) angle, others have questioned the patentability of inventions in specific areas such as stem cells, human embryos, and genetically modified organisms. Such patent cases have also given rise to fierce opposition from civil society/NGOs. Criticism from the perspective of ethics is however not limited to such ‘patents-on-life’ issues, but also involves questions regarding broad and upstream product patents (that hinder rather than foster innovation), the importance of openness and of sharing of knowledge, specific medical concerns, and the global justice dimension of patenting. The extent to

which the European patent system takes on board such ethical and societal considerations is however very limited.

From the perspective of *epistemology and science models*, the patent system has been criticized for not being able to deal with new modes of knowledge production ('mode2') and/or with technologies, such as large parts of biotechnology, that show characteristics of post-normal science (i.e. high levels of uncertainty, value disputes, high decision stakes, and high societal urgency). Given these characteristics knowledge production and exploitation (of which the patent system is part) is inherently linked to policy making (and to politics), and both should take place within extended societal communities.

From the perspective of *governance studies*, focusing on accountability and legitimacy, it has been argued that the European patent system is in fact a very closed system, a technocracy made up of legal and technical experts who at best interact with only those stakeholders directly involved in patenting practices (i.e. patent applicants) but hardly beyond the patent system as such. The European Patent Office (EPOff), as the supranational agency of the European Patent Organisation (EPOrg), has a high degree of autonomy and combines executive, quasi-judicial, and tacit legislative powers. This self-governance raises questions about transparency, accountability and democratic control. The system has insufficient formal and informal mechanisms that provide for 'checks and balances' by means of broader networks for dialogue and learning, which creates problems of democratic legitimacy. It has distinct characteristics of a so-called epistemic community: a network of professionals with shared normative principles and beliefs, shared causal beliefs, a shared notion of what constitutes valid knowledge, and with a common policy enterprise.

Related to the above, from the *perspective of RRI* the patent system has also been criticized for lack of inclusion of and responsiveness to societal stakeholders. RRI is a research and innovation strategy that highlights the importance of research and innovation contributing to societal goods, not creating undesirable side effects, and being developed in dialogue with society and in line with societal values. It implies that –through inclusive participatory approaches- societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes, with the values, needs and expectations of European society. For research and innovation to be responsible, it needs to address significant societal needs and challenges, it needs to actively engage and respond to a range of stakeholders, in order to anticipate potential problems, identify alternatives, and reflect on underlying values. Because patents are part of the overall research and innovation process, these requirements also apply to patent systems.

In defence of the patent system, it has been argued that patent systems are not meant to evaluate such broader societal issues. Patent law and its application should not involve other considerations than patentability; such considerations should be dealt with outside of the patent system. The only valid yardstick is how the patent system contributes to innovation. The traditional patent paradigm is then that inventors need to be rewarded for their R&D efforts by creating a long-term, enforceable, exclusive right to the use of that invention. Such exclusive rights create an incentive for R&D; the requirement to publish the invention further stimulates the diffusion of ideas. Within this paradigm the role of the patent system is straightforward. i.e. to establish whether the basic requirements for patentability (novelty, inventive step, and industrial applicability) are met.

The links between *patenting and innovation* are however much more complicated than this basic reward idea presupposes. The downside of exclusive rights is that monopolies are created which by definition distort markets. Patents furthermore impede the combination of new ideas and inventions and raise transaction costs (the anti-commons problem). In that sense patents may be detrimental to innovation rather than promote it. The empirical evidence about the link between innovation and patents is far from conclusive. More generally, the OECD has observed a striking paucity of economic evaluation of the patent system.

Another possibility is to see *patents as regulatory interventions* by the state on behalf of society that should be in service of society's interest. This view makes it very clear that granting patents comes with (economic, ethical) trade-offs and is essence a balancing act. Patents are privileges, not rights. Currently, patents are often viewed as legal entitlements rather than economic tools with costs, benefits, and relationships to other aspects of innovation. Despite its purpose, the patent system therefore remains virtually unconnected to other technology and innovation policies and operates from a rather broad and vague conceptualization of innovation. However, the patent system should not go for 'any innovation as such', and especially should not prioritize outdated vertical integration ('silo') approaches to innovation but should promote open innovation as much as possible. The patent system is a vehicle for knowledge diffusion and not for innovation *per se*. Taking this view on the European patent system as a starting point, the PATGOV project built on earlier diagnoses, but took the analysis an important step further by looking at **changes needed in the governance of the European patent system in order to substantially enhance its responsiveness to societal stakeholders and broader societal considerations, or -put more simply- to open the system up.**

RESEARCH UNDERTAKEN IN THE PATGOV PROJECT

The project used various research methods: analysis of academic literature, of secondary statistical data, of websites, policy documents and legislation, and interviews (under Chatham House rules) with key actors. It used a basic analytical framework which centred on two elements: willingness of key actors in the system to include (based on preferences and relative bargaining power), and capacity to include (based on change costs).

The project first analysed existing responsiveness mechanisms as used by the European Patent Organization (EPOrg), an international organization (IO) of 38 contracting states, with the European Patent Office (EPOff) as its executive branch. It also tentatively looked at IP Australia and the USPTO and their use of responsiveness mechanisms. It was found that such mechanisms are not abundant and not very well and/or frequently used. This is also true for so-called compulsory licensing (where patent holders are forced to license their patents to other parties), an instrument that has recently received renewed interest, also in light of the coronavirus pandemic.

The analyses then turned to the institutional set-up of the EPOrg, using a principal-agent approach. It was found that the EPOrg suffers from a multitude of agency issues, with ignorant primary principals (the contracting states), a highly symbiotic relationship between the supervisory principals (representatives from national patent offices) and the ultimate agent (the EPOff), and an inadequate incentive scheme. Similar problems were found in a comparative analysis that included the EPOrg, the European Union Industrial Property Office (EUIPO) and the Community Plant Variety Office (CPVO).

The project subsequently looked into potential changes in substantive patent law, especially into the use of liability rules rather than property rules in the patent system. It developed a three-pronged system of patents: (a) traditional patents with enhanced proportionality requirements, (b) inclusive patents with voluntary licensing, and (c) patents with compulsory licensing.

The final part of the project analysed the changes the Unitary Patent and the Unitary Patent Court may bring to the overall responsiveness of the system. It was found that in terms of institutional change the so-called patent package which introduced the UP/UPC was a missed opportunity. The UP Regulation and the UPC Agreement do however introduce some substantial improvements to patent law. This is interesting as use of these instruments for substantive patent law change comes with far less costs than EPC revision and can be used to that end in the future as well.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

To the contracting parties to the European Patent Convention

1-Meet and discuss the European patent system at regular times, as is prescribed in the EPC.

2-Explicitly state what the current function (i.e. the societal mission) of the European patent system is, in light of emerging technologies and open innovation.

3-Pending EPC revision, consider replacing the current representation by (heads of) national patent offices (NPOs) in the Administrative Council of the EPOrg, by representation directly from the ministerial level.

4-Invest in EPC revision, even though such a revision is costly given the large number of contracting parties.

5-Make the following revisions to the governance of the EPOrg:

- Replacement of the current EPOrg Administrative Council by:
 - o a Management Board (MB) in which the EPOff and the (heads of) NPOs are represented, and which is embedded in the EPOff organization. The EPOff president can however not be chair or vice-chair of this MB;
 - o a Governing Council (GC) made up of ministerial representatives from the contracting states;
 - o an Assembly made up of representatives from national parliaments and the European Parliament.
- Appointment of the EPOff president and vice-presidents by the GC;
- Separate status within the EPOrg for the Boards of Appeal (i.e. no longer embedded within the EPOff). Members of the Boards of Appeal are appointed by the GC. Decisions on suspension of members of Boards of Appeal are also made by the GC;
- Separate status within the EPOrg of the Board of Auditors. Members of the Board of Auditors are appointed by the GC. Decisions on suspension of members of the Board of Auditors are also made by the GC;
- Transfer of the (*de facto*) law making competencies of the current AC to the GC;
- Annual reporting from the MB to the GC, as well as regular external independent reviews/benchmarks of the EPOff;
- The Assembly has a deliberative and an advisory role; it makes recommendations to the GC on issues of patent law and on institutional issues;
- Limiting the financial dependency of the EPOrg on its clients, by letting the contracting states provide more base funding;
- The GC decides on fee levels and fee splitting between the EPOff and NPOs;
- Explicit and binding rules on participation of third parties in GC, MB and committee work, emphasizing the need for broad involvement and representation of such parties;
- Legal independent status for a Scientific Advisory Board, which advises the GC on broader issues relevant to the functioning of the patent system;
- Introduction of a simplified EPC revision procedure.

6-Consider the following changes in substantive patent law

- Balance the current traditional property based patents with the following instruments:
 - o enhanced patentability requirements for patents in emerging technologies, by means of explicitly addressing the *ordre public* and morality clause of art 53(a) EPC as a patentability requirement in well-defined cases;
 - o the introduction of a general proportionality requirement to counter overly broad patent claims;
 - o differentiation in patent protection length, taking into account that different technologies have different life cycles;
 - o allow renewal of previously unused patents under specific conditions only;
 - o alienation of patent rights to parties that do not commercially use these patents (NPEs, non-practising entities) within a certain period of time, should render these patents invalid by law.
- Introduce a new patent right, the so-called inclusive patent, based on the use of liability rules in combination with inclusive schemes, to supplement the traditional (property-rule based) patents. The basic difference between traditional patents (with the possibility of voluntary licensing schemes) and inclusive patents is that with inclusive patents inclusion is obligatory; with traditional patents the right holder is not obliged to include. With such inclusive patents FRAND rules provide the bottom-line for such inclusion, but the right holder is free to choose other schemes (patentleft, permissive licenses, or waivers). Such inclusive patents might be subject to simplified application procedures (registration patents, but with full examination upon request) and with the possibility in the application phase to change an application for an inclusive patent into an application for a traditional patent (or vice versa). Obviously, such changes are not allowed after the patent has been granted;
- Consider generic compulsory licensing of patents (i.e. statutory licensing) for specific types of inventions, such as medicines.
- Harmonise compulsory licensing rules, in order to reduce legal uncertainty and to prevent potential unfair competition.

To the (president of) the European Patent Office

1-Explicitly follow-up on third party observations and *amicus curiae* briefs in patent granting procedures.

2-Speed up the establishment of the Observatory. Make sure it is more than just an observatory, i.e. a real platform for debate. Broadly include NGOs and other societal actors.

3-Repeat the 2007 Scenarios exercise.

4-Re-instate the Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB).

5-Allow EPOff officials to actively engage in outreach activities, in their personal capacity (as is common in other international organizations).

To the EU institutions and UP/UPC Member States

- 1-Use the Unitary Patent and Unitary Patent Court as a game changer for the patent system. The UP/UPC does not only constitute differentiated integration within the EU, but within the EPOrg as well. Be a vanguard group for patent system reform.
- 2-Use revision of the UPC Agreement as a relatively easy way (compared to EPC revision) to change substantial patent law within the EU.
- 3-Use the first UP/UPC evaluation to evaluate the European patent system at large.
- 4-Reconder the set-up and functioning of the Select Committee within the EPOrg (currently modelled as mini-AC). Make it more inclusive and pro-active.
- 5-Consider integration of patent law and the law on plant variety rights.
- 6- Harmonise compulsory licensing rules in the EU, in order to reduce legal uncertainty and to prevent potential unfair competition.
- 7-Arrange a platform on patent issues, made up of MEPs and national parliamentarians.

-0-0-0-0-0-